

CLINICAL INSIGHT INTO THE THERAPEUTIC POTENTIAL OF TIKTAKSHEERA
BASTI IN KATIGATA VATA: A CASE STUDYDr. Mayuri R. Avhad^{1*}, Dr. Rakesh Sharma²¹Ph.D. Scholar, *Kayachikitsa* Dept., Guru Ravidas Ayurved University, Hoshiarpur, Punjab, India.²Ph.D. Guide, *Kayachikitsa* Dept., Guru Ravidas Ayurved University, Hoshiarpur, Punjab, India.

Article Received: 05 November 2026

Article Revised: 25 December 2026

Article Published: 01 January 2026

*Corresponding Author: Dr. Mayuri R. Avhad

Ph.D. Scholar, *Kayachikitsa* Dept., Guru Ravidas Ayurved University, Hoshiarpur, Punjab, India.DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18870954>**How to cite this Article:** Dr. Mayuri R. Avhad^{1*}, Dr. Rakesh Sharma². (2026) Clinical Insight Into The Therapeutic Potential Of Tiktaksheera Basti In Katigata Vata: A Case Study. *World Journal of Advance Healthcare Research*, 10(1), 140–142.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

In recent times, human life has become very stressful due to the factors such as lack of exercise, poor posture, occupational stress and prolonged standing, etc. These conditions contributed substantially to the increase in spinal disorders and joint disorders. Ayurveda classified such types of disorders under *Vataja Nanatmaja Vikara*, as well as under *Katigata Vata (Katigraha)*. These are degenerative condition characterized by structural changes to the lumbar vertebrae leading to low back pain, lumbar pain on movement, numbness, weakness and stiffness, etc. In the case of such types of *Vata* disorders, *Basti Chikitsa* is considered very useful therapeutic approach; amongst them *Tikta Ksheera Basti* is best suited for cases involving *Katigata Vata*. The purpose of this case study is to document a 35 year old female patient who was treated in the OPD with a classical presentation of *Katigata Vata*. The patient had previously received allopathic treatment; however, only temporary relief from pain was obtained. After the Ayurvedic treatment patient experienced considerable relief from pain, stiffness and associated symptoms.

KEYWORDS: *Ayurveda, Basti Chikitsa, Tikta Ksheera, Katigata Vata, Spinal Disorders.*

INTRODUCTION

Joints in India have become increasingly progressive with age, and also more common in females than males. Low-back pain is known as "*Katishoola*," and it has become a major health issue in recent times; numerous classical Ayurvedic texts used various names such as *Katigraha*, *Trika Shoola*, *Trika Graha* and *Prishtagraha*. *Kati Pradesh* is considered a major location for *Vata Dosha*. In *Katigraha*, *Vata Dosh*a becomes vitiated at its own site, causing pain and restriction to the *Sphikasthi* and *Prishtha Vankshan Aasthi*. As depicted in **Figure 1**, Ayurveda also classified various type of *Katigata Vata* based on causative factors.^[1-4]

Figure 1: Various types of *Katigata Vata* based on causative factors.

As mentioned above *Dhatukshaya Janya Katigata Vata* caused by aging, tissue loss or malnutrition, this condition results in dull, chronic discomfort. While *Margavarodha Janya Katigata Vata* is characterized by stiffness, heaviness and limited movement since *Vata's* route is blocked by *Ama* or *Kapha*.

In modern science similar type of condition termed as Spondylolisthesis which represents the act of slipping forward displacing one vertebra above another. The forward movement of one vertebra above and in relation of the other may cause spinal deformity; narrowing of the spinal canal and compression of the exiting spinal nerve roots. The anterior sliding of a lumbar vertebra is the hallmark of lumbar anterolisthesis, which manifests as lower back discomfort, tingling and numbness in the lower extremities, trouble walking and limited mobility. Spinal injury, aging-related degenerative changes and spinal malignancies are common etiological causes.^[4-6]

In the pathophysiology and treatment of these diseases, Ayurveda places a strong emphasis on the intimate connection between *Vata Dosha* and *Asthi Dhatu*. *Acharya* states that the main treatment for *Katigata Vata*

is *Basti Chikitsa*. This therapy boosts *Asthi Dhatu* and pacifies vitiated *Vata*. The *Tikta Dravya Siddha Ksheera Basti* specially considered very helpful for relieving symptoms and pathogenesis of *Katigata Vata*. Considering this fact present case report demonstrate efficacy of *Tiktaksheera Basti* in the management of *Katigata Vata*.^[5-7]

CASE REPORT

A 35-year-old woman came to the OPD complaining of *Katishoola* that had been radiating to *Ubhaya Pada*, *Sakashta Chankramana*, *Katistambha* and difficulty bending forward for the previous few months. The patient's medical history indicates that she had been using allopathic drugs for few months, but they only gave her short term comfort.

Clinical Examinations

Category	Parameter	Outcome
General Examination	General Condition	Moderate
	Pulse Rate	72/min
	Blood Pressure	120/70 mmHg
	Respiratory Rate	20/min
Systemic Examination	CVS	S1, S2 normal
	CNS	Conscious and normal behavior
	RS	Bilaterally equal and clear
	P/A	Soft and non-tender

Ashtavidha Pariksha

<i>Nadi</i>	<i>Mala</i>	<i>Mutra</i>	<i>Jivha</i>	<i>Shabda</i>	<i>Sparsha</i>	<i>Druk</i>	<i>Akriti</i>
72/min	<i>Samyak Pravritti</i>	<i>Samyak Pravritti</i>	<i>Niram</i>	<i>Spashta</i>	<i>Sheeta</i>	<i>Aaraktavarni</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>

Vikrita Strotas Parikshana

Several *Srotas* were seen to be involved in *Vikrita Strotas Parikshana*. The patient had *Ubhaya Pindikodveshtana* when they first appeared in the *Rasavaha Strotas*. There was evidence of *Katishoola* in the *Asthivaha Strotas*. Symptoms in the *Majjavaha Strotas* included tingling, numbness in both limbs. Symptoms of *Sakashta Utkatasana* and *Sakashta Chankramana* were also observed for same *Strota*.

History

Few years ago, the patient seemed to be doing well. She described how she experienced lumbar pain, gradually began to feel numbness and tingling in both lower limbs. Walking, climbing stairs, sitting for extended periods of time and lifting heavy objects all made the discomfort worse. She also started to have trouble sitting and walking.

Assessment and Observation

Assessment was carried out based on subjective parameters and grading score as mentioned below:

Symptom	GRADING SCORE			
	Absent	Mild	Moderate	Severe
<i>Katishoola</i>	0	1	2	3
<i>Sakashta Chankramana</i>	0	1	2	3
<i>Sakashta Utkatasana</i>	0	1	2	3
Tingling and Numbness	0	1	2	3
Morning Stiffness	0	1	2	3

TREATMENT PROTOCOL

✓ *Shodhana Chikitsa – Tikta Ksheera Basti*

The formulation of *Tikta Ksheera Basti* consisted of *Ksheera*, *Madhu*, *Sahacharadi Taila*, *Kalka* and *Saindhava*. The *Kalka* was prepared using equal proportions of *Guduchi*, *Tikta Patola*, *Chirayata* and

Yastimadhu. Following the traditional Ayurvedic procedure, sixteen parts water was added, the mixture was reduced to one-eighth of its initial volume to create the *Kwatha*. After then, equal parts of milk and water were added to this infusion. The *Basti dravya* was

prepared by mixing it according to the conventional Ayurvedic method.

Administration/Application of Therapy

In order to attain the best *Brimhana* impact, the therapy was given every day for 15 days, ensuring adequate *Dharana Kala* for proper retention and absorption. To improve therapeutic results, *Sthanik Swedana* and *Sthanik Abhyanga* with *Taila* were also performed in addition to *Basti* therapy.

RESULTS AND OBSERVATIONS

The patient showed significant symptomatic improvement in subjective parameters. Following

treatment, the patient's subjective parameters demonstrated a notable improvement in symptoms. From grade 3 to grade 2, *Katishoola's* intensity decreased. *Sakashta Chankramana* dropped from grade 3 to grade 1, demonstrating a significant improvement. *Sakashta Utkatasana* also made progress from grade 3 to grade 1. Complaints of tingling and numbness decreased to grade 2. Significant improvement was also seen in morning stiffness, which decreased from grade 3 to grade 1. Overall, the results show that after the intervention, the severity of the symptoms significantly decreased as mentioned in **Table 1**.

Table 1: Improvement in Assessment Parameters after the Therapy.

Symptom	Before Treatment	After Treatment
<i>Katishoola</i>	3	2
<i>Sakashta Chankramana</i>	3	1
<i>Sakashta Utkatasana</i>	3	1
Tingling and Numbness	3	2
Morning Stiffness	3	1

DISCUSSION

Tikta Ksheera Basti provides nourishment to the *Asthi Dhatu* and pacifies *Vata*. *Tikta Rasa Siddha Ksheera Basti* increases the rate of conversion of food to energy which supports proper formation of *Asthi Dhatu* and thereby decreases degeneration. *Sthanik Abhyanga* and *Swedana* oppose the *Ruksha* and *Sheeta* properties of *Vata* in the body by assisting in moisture and warmth, respectively. *Taila* has the *Snigdha*, *Guru* and *Ushna* properties thus assist in creating *Vata Shama* effect. This *Taila* also improves muscle tone and flexibility. *Madhu* and *Saindhava* promote the absorption of the medicines used through topical application and can help to remove *Doshas* from the area of application.^[8-10]

CONCLUSION

For the treatment of *Katigata Vata*, a combination of *Sthanik Abhyanga* with *Taila*, *Swedana* and *Tikta Ksheera Basti* works appreciably. Significant symptom alleviation was achieved without side effects from the therapy. *Katigata Vata* can be efficiently managed with *Tikta Ksheera Basti*, especially in conditions involving the degenerative lumbar spine. To confirm these results, more clinical research with bigger sample numbers is necessary.

REFERENCES

1. Kasinath shastri (editor), Charak Samita Part-2 siddhisthan 1st chapter, shloka no.39, 4th edition, chaukhamba saskrit sansthan, Varanasi, 1994; 886.
2. Middleton K, Fish DE. Lumbar spondylosis: clinical presentation and treatment approaches. *Curr Rev Musculoskelet Med.*, 2009 Jun; 2(2): 94-104.
3. Davidson's Principals and Practice of Medicine, 23rd edition, 2018, Edited by Stuart H.Ralston, Ian D. Penman, Mark WJ Strachall, Richard P. Hobson, Published by Elsevier Publication, 1135.
4. Agnivesha, Charaka Samhita- Part - 1, Sootrasthana, Adhyaya 20, 4th edition, 1994, Edited with Vidyotini Hindi commentary by Pt. Kashinath Shastri, Published by Chaukhamba Sanskrit Pratishthana, Varanasi, 271.
5. Agnivesha, Charaka Samhita- Part - 1, Sootrasthana, Adhyaya 28, 4th edition, 1994, Edited with Vidyotini Hindi commentary by Pt. Kashinath Shastri, Published by Chaukhamba Sanskrit Pratishthana, Varanasi, 432.
6. Dr. Ramesh Sonwane, Panchakarma Vigyan, 1st Edition, Published by Saraswati Prakashan, Aurangabad, 2015; Chapter 6th: P 271.
7. Sharangdhara, Sharangdhara Samhita, Madhyamakhandha, Adhyaya 2, 4th edition, 1994, Edited with Krishna Hindi Commentary by Acharya Shree Radhakrishna Parashar, Published by Baidyanath Ayurved Bhavan, Nagpur, 224.
8. Sharma RK, Dash B Charaka Samhita, Sutrasthana. 2013; Vol. 6 Varanasi Chaukhamba Sanskrit Series Office Ch. 28, Ver. 27.
9. Kalpana Gaikwad, Ramesh Sonwane and Neralkar UK. A case study on the role of Tikta Ksheera Basti in the management of Katigata vata with special reference to Lumbar Spondylosis. *Int. J. Res. Ayurveda Pharm.*, 2023; 14(5): 108-110.
10. Kaalia, Neelam; Bhatted, Santosh Kumar; Acharya, S. H. Effect of Panchatikta Ksheera basti with Kati basti in Katishoola w. s. r lumbar disc degeneration – A clinical study. *Indian Journal of Health Sciences and Biomedical Research (KLEU)*, Jan–Apr 2021; 14(1): 108-112.